

Studies on Polymeric Complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with *o*-Hydroxy Thiosemicarbazones

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Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes with six *o*-hydroxy thiosemicarbazones such as 2-OH, 5-CH₃ aceto/propio/benzophenone thiosemicarbazones and 2-OH-5-Cl aceto/propio/benzophenone thiosemicarbazones are prepared. The analytical data shows them to have 1 : 1 composition of M : L. The Cu(II) complexes have normal magnetic moments but Ni(II) complexes have abnormally low magnetic moments.

MANY polymeric complexes with thiosemicarbazones have been reported¹⁻³. Polymers containing a metal ion, bonded to an organic ligand may have unusual thermal and electrical properties endowed by the presence of a metal ion¹. Some of the derivatives of thiosemicarbazones have also attracted special attention due to their antibacterial⁴, antifungal⁵ and antitumor⁶ activities.

Experimental

Materials and methods: The chemicals used were all of AnalaR grade. The ligands were prepared by refluxing *o*-hydroxy ketones with thiosemicarbazide in alcohol for about an hour. They were precipitated by pouring on ice. They were recrystallised from alcohol. The following six ligands (H₂L) were used for the preparation of metal complexes.

2-Hydroxy 5-methyl aceto/propio/benzophenone thiosemicarbazones. 2-Hydroxy-5-chloro aceto/propio/benzophenone thiosemicarbazones.

Preparation of complexes: To a metal solution of CuSO₄·5H₂O or NiSO₄·7H₂O an equimolar ligand solution in rectified spirit was added. The pH of the solution was maintained between 5.5 to 6.5 by means of acetate buffer. The solutions were refluxed for half an hour on a water bath. The solids which slowly separated were filtered and washed with hot water and alcohol to remove excess metal ions and unreacted ligands respectively. The complexes were dried and stored in vacuum at room temperature. They were not recrystallised because of their insolubility in almost all common organic solvents.

Magnetic moments of solid complexes were determined at room temperature on a Gouy balance using solid Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a standard. Absorption spectra were measured on Toshniwal Spectrophotometer in DMF. IR spectra were taken in nujol. Conductance was measured in DMF. Since the complexes were insoluble in almost all common solvents, molecular weights could not be determined in any manner except by Rast method only using camphor as a solvent. TGA was done on TGA 2TR supplied by M/s. Laboratories, Calcutta, and DTA on DTA steuteill, Vel Laborelektronik. All the results are given in the Table.

Results and Discussion

The experimental analysis shows the complexes to be 1 : 1 :: M : L. The ligands thus behave as dibasic acids and may be represented as H₂L. The phenolic -OH and the -SH formed on tautomeric migration of proton from NH to S seem to get deprotonated on complex formation. The C=S thus becomes C-S- on complexation. Molecular weight determinations by Rast method did not give reproducible results. In view of the low solubility in all solvents the complexes could be polymeric. The low conductivity (about 10 mhos) confirms the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. TGA residues are in accordance with the suggested composition which is given above. The DTA curves do not show any endothermic peak at 120-190° suggesting absence of water in the complexes.

The magnetic moments of the Cu(II) complexes vary between 1.7 and 2.0 B.M. indicating one unpaired electron and no metal-metal bond. The magnetic moments of Ni(II) complexes are low and seem to point to a structure for these complexes which is essentially square planar with C_{2v} symmetry. Such low magnetic moments are known^{7,8}. The anomalous moments could be due to polymerisation.

IR spectra of all the complexes show two bands around 3400 and 3250 cm⁻¹. They are ascribed to ν_{as} and ν_s stretching vibrations respectively of the NH₂ groups which are non-coordinating. There is no band between 2500-2600 cm⁻¹. This confirms that there is no SH group. The weak IR band in all ligands at 1175 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C=S stretching vibration. It is absent in complexes. A band near 820 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C-S vibration. This would indicate bonding to metals through sulphur as CS⁻ acid function. C=N vibration is found in the ligands and complexes at about 1590 cm⁻¹. We observe, further, that the C=N stretching frequency is split in complexes indicating the presence of two different types of C=N groups in complexes. This seems to suggest the complex formation for the ligand in the mercapto form. ν_{MN} and ν_{MO} bands are observed at around 530 cm⁻¹ and 450 cm⁻¹ respectively. The ligands show a broad band at

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TABLE—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND THERMAL DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	% Metal found (calcd.)	% Sulphur found (calcd.)	% Nitrogen found (calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	Thermal Analysis % residue found (calcd.)
1.	2-OH-5Cl aceto tsc Cu(II)	20.78 (20.82)	10.38 (10.47)	13.61 (13.75)	1.9	21.5 (20.95)
2.	2-OH-5Cl propio tsc Cu(II)	19.81 (19.92)	10.00 (10.09)	13.24 (13.16)	1.75	25.9 (25.3)
3.	2-OH-5Cl benzo tsc Cu(II)	17.24 (17.81)	8.65 (8.72)	11.88 (11.44)	2.05	22.4 (21.7)
4.	2-OH-5Me aceto tsc Cu(II)	22.39 (22.32)	11.18 (11.24)	14.71 (14.76)	1.95	28.52 (27.98)
5.	2-OH-5Me propio tsc Cu(II)	21.4 (21.29)	10.65 (10.71)	14.15 (14.06)	1.7	26.05 (26.63)
6.	2-OH-5Me benzo tsc Cu(II)	18.30 (18.25)	9.20 (9.23)	12.21 (12.11)	1.72	23.7 (22.96)
7.	2-OH-5Cl aceto tsc Ni(II)	19.39 (19.55)	10.82 (10.66)	14.15 (13.99)	1.1	25.05 (24.82)
8.	2-OH-5Cl propio tsc Ni(II)	18.76 (18.69)	10.11 (10.18)	13.25 (13.36)	0.75	23.91 (23.82)
9.	2-OH-5Cl benzo tsc Ni(II)	16.15 (16.20)	8.72 (8.83)	11.48 (11.57)	0.77	20.78 (20.92)
10.	2-OH-5Me aceto tsc Ni(II)	21.07 (20.98)	11.96 (11.44)	15.08 (15.01)	0.83	26.84 (26.7)
11.	2-OH-5Me propio tsc Ni(II)	19.90 (19.98)	10.93 (10.86)	14.21 (14.3)	0.85	25.62 (25.41)
12.	2-OH-5Me benzo tsc Ni(II)	17.25 (17.2)	9.42 (9.26)	12.37 (12.29)	0.76	22.1 (21.86)

Aceto tsc = Acetophenone thiosemicarbazone ; propio tsc = propiophenone thiosemicarbazone ;
benzo tsc = benzophenone thiosemicarbazone.

about 3550 cm^{-1} due to the OH group. The latter band is absent in all the complexes and must be getting used up in complex-formation.

R = OH, Cl
R' = OH, C₂H₅, C₆H₅
M = Cu(II), Ni(II)

All the complexes have an absorption band in DMF solution at 375 nm and 415 nm. These two bands are also present in all the six ligands. In the Cu(II) complexes, over and above these two bands, three ill-defined bands around 520 nm ($\epsilon = 475$), 560 nm ($\epsilon = 350$) and 630 nm ($\epsilon = 160$) are also observed. Cu(II) square planar complexes can have the following transitions :

The three bands observed in solution in DMF could be due to the above transitions.

In Ni(II) complexes also three weak bands are observed around 530 nm ($\epsilon = 200$), 570 nm ($\epsilon = 100$) and 640 nm ($\epsilon = 50$). Square planar Ni(II) complexes can have the following transitions :

The three bands could be due to the above transitions.

The discussion on assignment of spectral transition is based on an idealised D_{4h} symmetry. Some of the bands are found to be broad and unsymmetrical suggesting their composite nature.

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